

**IMPACT OF THE ABSENCE OF EPAS IN MULTIPROFESSIONAL RESIDENCES
IN BRAZIL: A SCOPE REVIEW**

IMPACTO DE LA AUSENCIA DE EPAS EN LAS RESIDENCIAS MULTIPROFESIONALES EN
BRASIL: UNA REVISIÓN DEL ALCANCE

IMPACTO DA AUSÊNCIA DAS EPAS NAS RESIDÊNCIAS MULTIPROFISSIONAIS NO
BRASIL: UMA REVISÃO DE ESCOPO

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Abstract

Entrustable professional activities are widely recognized as valuable tools for evaluating physicians in various roles. However, their application can be extended to other health professions when adapted to specific contexts, such as multiprofessional residencies in primary health care. This study aimed to assess the impacts of using these activities in both multiprofessional and uniprofessional residencies. The methodology followed the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) framework for scoping reviews and the PRISMA-ScR structure. The process involved six steps: definition of population, concept, and context (PCC); establishment of eligibility criteria; identification of best sources of information; selection of evidence sources; synthesis of results; and elaboration of the conclusion. A total of 592 records were identified,

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with 30 studies selected after screening. These were analyzed according to key variables and domains. The main emerging themes were: a) changes in curriculum assessment; b) development of specific activities for the target audience; c) positive outcomes from the use of such activities; d) integration with other assessment tools; and e) educator engagement. The findings indicate that the use of entrustable professional activities is not yet standardized across higher education institutions. However, when implemented, they have proven effective and promising for strengthening continuing education, particularly within the Brazilian public health system (SUS). Further research is recommended to explore their benefits in improving the quality of primary health care led by multiprofessional residents.

Keywords: Entrustable professional activities; Multiprofessional residency; Competency assessment.

Resumen

Las actividades profesionales confiables son reconocidas como herramientas valiosas para evaluar a los médicos en diversas funciones. Sin embargo, su aplicación puede extenderse a otras profesiones de la salud si se adaptan a contextos específicos, como en el caso de las residencias multiprofesionales en atención primaria. Este estudio tuvo como objetivo evaluar los impactos del uso de estas actividades en residencias multiprofesionales y uniprofesionales. Se utilizó la metodología del Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) para revisiones de alcance, siguiendo también la estructura PRISMA-ScR. El proceso incluyó seis etapas: definición de población, concepto y contexto (PCC); establecimiento de criterios de elegibilidad; identificación de las mejores fuentes de información; selección de evidencias; síntesis de resultados; y elaboración de la conclusión. Se identificaron 592 registros, de los cuales se seleccionaron 30 estudios tras la criba. Los estudios se analizaron según variables y dominios relevantes. Los principales temas identificados fueron: a) cambios en la evaluación curricular; b) desarrollo de actividades específicas para el público estudiado; c) resultados positivos en su uso; d) integración con otras herramientas de evaluación; y e) compromiso del cuerpo docente. Se concluye que el uso de actividades profesionales confiables aún no está estandarizado entre las instituciones de educación superior. No obstante, cuando se aplican, muestran eficacia y potencial para mejorar la educación permanente, especialmente en el contexto del SUS. Se recomienda ampliar e investigar más a fondo sus beneficios en la formación de residentes multiprofesionales y en la calidad del cuidado en salud primaria.

Palabras clave: Actividades profesionales confiables; Residencia multiprofesional; Evaluación de competencias.

Resumo

As atividades profissionais confiáveis são reconhecidas como ferramentas valiosas na avaliação de médicos em suas diversas funções. No entanto, seu uso pode ser estendido a outras profissões da saúde, desde que adaptado aos contextos específicos, como ocorre nas residências multiprofissionais em atenção básica. Este estudo teve como objetivo avaliar os impactos da utilização dessas atividades nas residências multiprofissionais e uniprofissionais. A metodologia adotada foi a do Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) para revisões de escopo, seguindo também a estrutura do PRISMA-SCR. O processo envolveu seis etapas: definição da população, conceito e contexto (PCC); estabelecimento dos critérios de elegibilidade; identificação das melhores fontes de informação; seleção das fontes de evidência; síntese dos resultados; e elaboração da conclusão. Foram identificados 592 registros, dos quais 30 estudos foram selecionados após a triagem. Esses estudos foram analisados conforme variáveis e domínios relevantes. Os principais temas identificados foram: a) mudanças nos modelos de avaliação curricular; b) desenvolvimento de atividades confiáveis específicas para os públicos estudados; c) resultados positivos no uso dessas atividades; d) integração com outras ferramentas avaliativas; e) envolvimento dos educadores no processo. Conclui-se que o uso das atividades

profissionais confiáveis ainda não é padronizado entre as instituições de ensino superior. No entanto, quando implementadas, mostram-se eficazes e promissoras para a qualificação da educação permanente, especialmente no contexto do SUS. Recomenda-se a ampliação e aprofundamento de pesquisas sobre seus efeitos na formação de residentes multiprofissionais e na qualidade do cuidado em saúde primária.

Palavras-chave: Atividades profissionais confiáveis; Residência Multiprofissional; Avaliação de competências.

Introduction

Among the ten most competitive courses in Brazilian higher education, programs in the health field stand out, such as Medicine, Nursing, Psychology, and Dentistry. Although the Medicine course is the most competitive, it accounts for only 11% of the available spots in this area, while the other programs concentrate most of the opportunities (Brasil, 2023). Professionals graduated from these courses, along with some medical specialties, make up the multiprofessional health teams (e-multi), playing an essential role in the functioning of the Unified Health System (SUS) (Brasil, 2017; Brasil, 2019; Brasil, 2020). However, the quality of training for these professionals remains a challenge, as not all higher education institutions achieve satisfactory results according to the criteria of the Ministry of Education (MEC) (Brasil, 2022). In this context, tools such as Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) become strategic for more accurately assessing student competence, especially during professional practice, ensuring a more qualified performance aligned with the needs of the SUS (Flor, et al., 2022; Cate, 2005).

Residencies in the health area constitute a postgraduate model characterized by the predominance of practical experience in healthcare services. This model gained prominence for its strategic role in consolidating Continuing Health Education (CHE). Initially exclusive to physicians, multiprofessional residencies were implemented only in 2025, under the management of the National Commission of the Multiprofessional Residency in Health (CNRMS). This expansion aims to ensure that EPS achieves its objectives by qualifying training processes, and reconfiguring daily work in health, promoting the development of skills in an integrated and collaborative manner (Brasil, 2005; Brasil, 2014; Brasil, 2017).

However, the training of residents faces several challenges. A systematic review by Flor *et al* (2022), highlights barriers that vary according to the environment and the infrastructure available in the municipality or state. Among the common obstacles are the resistance of professionals to integrate residents into practical activities and the lack of preparedness of preceptors and tutors, factors that hinder the overcoming of traditional practices and compromise the objectives of EPS. To face these difficulties, the standardization of competencies becomes essential, ensuring that practical scenarios are effective strategies in EPS policy.

In this context, Reliable Professional Activities stand out as a promising tool to enhance the training of healthcare professionals in line with the demands of the SUS. EPAS assesses skills and competencies, ensuring that professionals work with autonomy and safety (Lau *et al*, 2020). Despite their relevance, the use of EPAs remains more frequent in specialized care, especially among physicians, while their application in Primary Health Care (PHC) and among multiprofessional residents is still limited (Moore *et al*, 2023). This gap highlights the need for studies that investigate the implementation and impacts of EPAs in this context, contributing to strengthening multiprofessional training.

Through this scope review, it is expected to provide support for the improvement of formative practices in multiprofessional residencies, with a focus on Primary Health Care (PHC). The main objective is to evaluate the impacts of using Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) in multiprofessional and uniprofessional residencies. In addition, the study aims to encourage reflection of the role of EPAs as an essential tool for preceptors and tutors to monitor and assess residents' ability to perform activities autonomously. By promoting more effective training aligned with the population's needs, it is expected that this review will contribute to strengthening the quality of care in PHC in Brazil.

Methods

- Protocol and Registration

The study is configured as a scoping review, conducted according to the methodology of the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI, 2015), which will follow the protocol

of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA – ScR) with updates proposed by Tricco *et al* (2018).

According to the need to address the main elements of this type of study, according to JBI, Population/Concept/Context (PCC) were defined as follows:

Population: Learning environments at the level of primary basic, or secondary health care, such as Basic Health Units (UBS) and Emergency Care Units (UPA).

Concept: EPAs or competency-based educational activities.

Context: Postgraduate students in a *latu sensu* course in accordance with the regulations established by the National Commission for Multiprofessional Health Residency (CNRMS) and Law 11.129 of 2005 (Brasil, 2017). Contexto: Pós-graduandos em curso *latu sensu* de acordo com as normas regulamentadas pela Comissão Nacional de Residência Multiprofissional em Saúde (CNRMS) e pela Lei 11.129 de 2005 (Brasil, 2017).

- Eligibility criteria

Any studies related to EPAs and multiprofessional residency will be considered, specifically articles or studies that meet the following criteria: (a) Publication period between 2014 and 2024; (b) Language: English, Spanish and Portuguese; (c) Types of literature: all types of literature will be searched, including not limited to descriptive studies, interventional studies, reviews; (d) All undergraduate fields in health sciences that can integrate and participate in multiprofessional teams in primary and secondary healthcare; € EPAs or a multiprofessional profession must be mentioned in the title or abstract.

- Sources of Information

To identify potentially relevant documents, the following electronic bibliographic databases were searched from 2014 to November 2024: Virtual Health Care Library (BVS) with access to Lilacs and the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), as well as Medline via PubMed. Search strategies were developed and refined interactively using free-text keywords related to multiprofessional residency and EPAs, which were combined using Boolean operators. Search results were exported to Excel, and

duplicates were removed according to a specific formula. All search sequences are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Search strings for electronic databases.

Descriptors	BVS	SciELO	PubMed	Total
"Entrustable Professional Activities" AND "PRIMARY CARE"	25	0	41	66
"Entrustable Professional Activities" AND "SUS"	12	7	0	19
"Entrustable Professional Activities" AND "INTERPROFESSIONAL"	50	0	52	102
"Entrustable Professional Activities" AND "MULTIPROFESSIONAL"	7	0	0	7
"Entrustable Professional Activities" AND "RESIDENCE"	412	0	3	415
Total incluído	506	7	96	609

Source: Authors.

- Selection of sources of evidence

The study screening was conducted Through a four-step process. First, the Authors conducted database research, analyzing which Boolean operators were most appropriate in accordance with the number of studies found within the eligibility criteria. After this identification, the titles were analyzed, and those consistent with the research were exported to an Excel spreadsheet, including the title, link, and year of publication. Subsequently, another author used Excel tools to identify duplicate titles and began reading the abstracts of the selected articles. Finally, a third author conducted a full reading of the articles to verify their eligibility while the second author reviewed the selections made by the first author. Articles that were not clearly considered eligible by both reviewers were discussed with a third reviewer.

- Data chart creation process

A data chart form was developed collaboratively by two reviewers to determine which information to extract. During the full Reading of the selected studies, relevant information was extracted regarding the main characteristics of the study and the competencies that a resident should acquire during residency or before entering. Data abstraction on the characteristics of the literature, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Data charts of variables and domains related to the description of the article.

Element of PCC	Item / domain	Description
Population	Year	Year of publication
	Author(s)	List of author(s)
	Geographical Localization	Country in which the institution is seated
Context	Context	Level of Health
	Professional category	Undergraduate, postgraduate, bachelor's degree
Concept	Characteristics of EPAS	Listed EPAS and how they are characterized
	Effects	If any effect was reported, which ones were described using which results

Source: Authors.

- Summary of Results

We grouped the studies according to professional category, the level of attention to health, and the frequency of other information described qualitatively according to relevance and other general findings.

Results

- Selection of evidence sources

After the process of verification and removal of duplicates, a total of 592 articles were identified from searchers in the selected electronic databases. Based on the title and abstract, 335 were excluded, leaving 87 articles for full-text reading for possible eligibility. From these readings, 57 were removed for the following reasons: 47 did not address E-multi or did not list the EPAs or conclusions about their use, 1 was a commentary, 8 were not freely accessible, 2 were not available for reading, and 1 was duplicated. The remaining 29 studies were considered eligible for this review. The representation of this process is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Flowchart of literature selection according to (JBI, 2015).

Source: Authors.

In this scoping review, 20 studies were identified that address EPAs in the context of multiprofessional teams (E-Multi) in primary health care (PHC). The conclusions of the authors of these studies are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 – Summary of the main conclusions about EPAs from the included literature according to professional category.

Professional category	Main conclusions about EPAs
Odontology	EPAs can provide a necessary catalyst to enhance dental education for graduate dentists who embrace an expanded role as primary care providers (Latta; Radniecki, 2024).
Nursing	EPAs can be feasible as na effective workplace-bases assessment tool in e-portfolios for interns and supervisors (Alexander et al., 2022).
Odontology	It suggests a real commitment among educators to recognize the vital role that oral health training plays in shaping in shaping the provision of primary care in the future (Goodell et al., 2019).
Pharmacy	By aligning assessment practices with EPAs, competencies can be more achievable (Yu et al., 2024).
Pharmacy	More EPAs should be developed for the clinical pharmacy profession, following the example of medical education (Bozic et al., 2024).
Pharmacy	It highlights the importance of refining other assessment tools to align with the EPAs (Nasser et al., 2024).
Medicine, Nursing, Pharmacy, Dietetic	Validated and reproducible structures, such as EPAs, assist in the advancement of the workforce, education, and practice (Merolli; Gray, 2024).

Nursing and the doctors' support team	Supports the involvement of non-physician team members in the development process of EPAs for training programs in other specialties (Van Keulen et al., 2024).
Pharmacy	EPAs were rarely mentioned When referring to direct patient care (Hunziker; Newman, 2023).
Odontology	Working with EPAs is generally well received and applicable in dental education (Hissink et al., 2022).
Pharmacy	The frequency with which the use of EPA assessment competencies is reported varies considerably depending on the task being assessed, the role of the pharmacist, and the status of the preceptor, among other factors (Scott et al., 2021).
Nursing	The development of specific EPAs for nursing care and practices can provide nursing programs with a guide to assist in curriculum planning and a foundation for developing assessment tools for assignments. The lack of familiarity with EPAs in nursing education may pose implementation challenges for EPAs (Lau et al., 2020).
Odontology	It has been reported that EPAs are essential for patient safety and resident education (Cully et al., 2024).
Fisioteraphy	EPAs provide meaningful information about progression towards competence for other stakeholders, such as health professions educators, health system leaders, and patients (Holleran, et al., 2023).
Nursing	EPAs are an effective way to assess how the team performs interventions in the clinical environment. Participants noted the need for possible limitations to be included in the EPAs, such as restrictions around high-acuity areas for certain levels/trained teams (Maguire et al., 2023).
Odontology	EPAs present a unique opportunity to rethink student assessment and progression toward readiness for practice, while simultaneously increasing confidence in predicting future performance and ensuring student trust (Quinonez et al., 2023).
Pharmacy	EPAs clarify assessment expectations by setting a standard for reference. For educators, EPAS describes professional skills as a framework for documenting student progression, within the program. For students, EPAs provide a basis for setting goals, measuring progress, and developing self-reflection skills (Elmes; Tekian; Jarrett, 2023).
Pharmacy and Nursing	The articles reviewed for the development of the EPA framework indicated that medical and pharmacy educators recognize the importance of mapping the development of EPAs for the university curriculum and any existing competency frameworks to translate educational theory into clinical practice (Abeyaratne; Galbraith, 2023).
Dietetic	The educational impact of the toll is high because assessing against the EPAs multiple times throughout the internships identifies specific areas for improvement required by individual students, while also generating data that can track the cohort's performance in the workplace (Bramley; Forsyth; Mckenna, 2023).
Nursing	Some deficiencies were identified in the EPAs, such as lack of clarity in the title, objectives, and description, which justify further refinement. In addition, the lack of familiarity with the use of EPAs in nursing education and feelings of inadequacy and unpreparedness reported by clinical preceptors may be challenging for the future implementation (Zhou et al., 2022).
Nursing	Program directors should adjust the expected supervisionconfidence level at various stages of training according to the complexity of individual EPAs (Chiang et al., 2022).
Odontology	Some challenges have been identified for the implementation of EPAs, mainly the lack of experience in designing and assessing EPAs in practice and the resistance to this type of assessment from trainers/supervisors (Kelly et al., 2022).
Nursing	The development of specific EPAs for undergraduate nursing programs can provide an opportunity to have a standardized language to assess student 'progress toward competence in nursing (Al-Moteri et al., 2021).

Nursing	It emphasizes that for the implementation of EPAs there is a need to describe competencies in relation to telehealth activities, rather than an overview of telehealth competencies (Latta; Radniecki, 2024).
Nursing, physiotherapy, nutrition	There are important components of activities that do not naturally fit into the definition of an EPA, such as collaborative interprofessional skills and attitudes (Van Houwelingen et al., 2016).
Odontology	The evaluation shows that working with EPAs is generally well received and that EPAs are applicable in dental education (Ten Cate; Piscina, 2020).
Nursing	The development of EPAS specific to nursing care and practices can provide nursing programs with a guide to assist in curriculum planning and a foundation for developing assessment tools for assignments (Hissink et al., 2022).
Pharmacy	Continuous efforts are necessary to improve the structure, content, and delivery of Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs), ensuring broader coverage of EPAs for sustained improvement (Lau et al., 2020).
Medicine, Nursing, Pharmacy, Public Health	EPAs for global health can be useful for academic institutions and other organizations to guide the evaluation of interns in education and training programs in health professions (Nasser et al., 2024).

Fonte: Autoria própria.

Discussion

- Summary of the evidence

This scoping review addressed the use of Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) in the assessment of the multiprofessional residents in primary health care. The application of filter by profession was necessary to capture a sufficient yet heterogeneous body of literature, revealing a significant gap in data specific to this audience. This limitation underscores the need to redesign the evaluation processes for health residents, especially for those who will become specialists in primary health care (Latta; Radniecki, 2024).

EPAs are essential tools for professional training, as they ensure the development of competencies aligned with the demands of the Unified Health System (SUS) and public policies. By defining reliable activities, they establish standards of quality and safety in patient care, as well as guide curricula that are more practical and focused on real needs. According to Research (Hennus et al., 2022), EPAs can be recognized by legal bodies, reinforcing the importance of a clear and reliable formulation of these activities, which must be certifiable.

Moreover, EPAs integrate theory and practice, preparing professionals to work collaboratively in multidisciplinary teams. By focusing on observable activities, they allow objective assessments of student process, identifying gaps and strengthening critical areas. This approach improves the quality of training and aligns competencies with the needs of the population. According to a recent study (Jones-Caar et al., 2024), EPAs promote progressive Confidence, which is essential for the development of complex and interpersonal skills.

Previous reviews on EPAs in multiprofessional contexts highlight the importance of standardizing assessments and integrating essential competencies into training. For example, a study (Alexander et al., 2022) focusing on nursing education demonstrated the need for clear criteria to evaluate students and the potential impacts of EPAs on clinical practice. Another review (Moore et al., 2023) pointed out the predominance of EPAs in post-licensure medicine, with skills applicable to different professions. Additionally, research (Goodell et al., 2019) emphasized the integration of oral health as a critical component in primary health care, reinforcing the relevance of multiprofessional approaches.

Preceptors play a central role in this process of restructuring as they are responsible for guiding the specificities of each professional category and directing residents in theoretical-practical education (Whitehouse, 1998). The scarcity of studies on evaluation methods during residencies can be better explored Through reports from professionals who have already complete or are in the final stage of their residency, allowing the mapping of needs observed during their training (Latta; Radniecki, 2024; Goodell et al., 2019).

To expand the use of EPAs in the national context, it is essential that the Multiprofessional Residency Commission (COREMU) establish standardized evaluation parameters, since this body coordinates, organizes, and supervises multiprofessional residency programs in a more effective and participatory manner (Pacheco et al., 2022; Schumacher et al., 2024). The applicability of EPA results in professional practice is widely recognized, as they promote the integration of essential technical and interpersonal competencies for safe and effective care. According to (Chiang et al., 2022), EPAs facilitate progressive assessment and the development of clinical skills, ensuring that professionals are prepared to assume responsibilities gradually and under supervision.

The study of EPAs has been gaining prominence in recent Years, especially since 2019 (Meyer et al., 2019). This growth has brought with it References for the proper development of these activities, such as the 12 tips proposed by Hennis *et al.* (2022) for medicine, which can be adapted for other professional categories. This adaptation can facilitate the expansion of EPAs beyond medicine, as well as the use of complementary assessment tools (Bozic et al., 2024).

In the view of the above, it is understood that the integration of clinical practice and continuous supervision allows residents to gain greater autonomy and professional skills relevant to primary health care. However, evaluations of the direct impact of EPAs on these training programs and on the development of specific skills are still scarce, which limits the understanding of the effects of this approach on the quality of care and professional training in the context of primary care (Carter et al., 2024; Cutrer et al., 2020).

Scoping reviews, as a methodology, present significant strengths for mapping concepts and evidence in emerging or complex areas. According to the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI, 2015), this approach allows for the identification of knowledge gaps, the synthesis of heterogeneous evidence, and the exploration of broad themes without strict restrictions regarding the type of study or methodological design. Complementing this perspective, Tricco et al. (2018) emphasize Through the PRISMA-ScR extension, that scoping reviews follow a systematic and transparent process, ensuring methodological rigor and replicability. These characteristics make scoping reviews an essential tool for researchers and professionals seeking to understand complex contexts and guide evidence-based decisions.

- Limitations

When it comes to EPAs in medical residences, there is a more detailed attention to the specific skills and competencies that residents must develop, demonstrating na emphasis on the acquisition and assessment of practical and theoretical competencies necessary for safe and efficient professional practice, which is rarely found When discussing other health professionals. Although there are some articles addressing multiprofessional residencies in Brazil, most of the available studies still predominantly

focus on medical residencies in hospital settings, with limited emphasis on competencies in tertiary healthcare.

Conclusion

This scoping review mapped the aspects of EPAs in multiprofessional residencies, highlighting curriculum changes and the standardization of competency assessment, the focused use on non-medical professional categories and primary care, the management of multiple assessment tools, and the suitability of educators. Although the limited number of studies revealed a gap in the literature on EPAs in RMS and in primary care, the study encourages future research on the effectiveness of EPAS in promoting professional autonomy and safety, as well as their benefits for the quality of primary healthcare, to consolidate the contribution of multiprofessional residencies primary care in Brazil.

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